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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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O‘ZBEKISTON TURIZMIDA GIGIYENA VA SANITARIYA MADANIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAHLIL VA TAKLIFLAR

Nishonova Hosila

Mirzo Ulug‘bek nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali

Kirish

So‘nggi yillarda O‘zbekiston turizm sohasida jadal rivojlanish bosqichiga kirib, xorijiy va ichki sayyohlar oqimi yil sayin ortib bormoqda. Bu esa, bir tomondan, mamlakat iqtisodiy salohiyatini oshirishga xizmat qilsa, boshqa tomondan — xizmat ko‘rsatish sifatini, ayniqsa, sog‘liq va xavfsizlik bilan bog‘liq jihatlarni xalqaro talablar darajasiga olib chiqishni taqozo etadi. Xizmat ko‘rsatish sohasida, xususan, mehmonxona va restoran infratuzilmasida gigiyena va sanitariya madaniyati muhim mezon sifatida turistik ob‘ektlarning obro‘sini belgilovchi asosiy omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada turizm sohasida gigiyena va sanitariya talablarining ahamiyati, xalqaro standartlar (ISO, HACCP) asosida ularning qo‘llanishi, shuningdek, O‘zbekiston misolida mavjud holat tahlil qilinadi va rivojlantirish bo‘yicha takliflar ilgari suriladi.

Gigiyena va sanitariya madaniyati: tushuncha va ahamiyati

Gigiyena — inson salomatligini saqlash va mustahkamlashga xizmat qiluvchi shaxsiy va jamoat tozaligini ta‘minlash tizimi bo‘lsa, sanitariya esa — atrof-muhit, oziq-ovqat, suv va havo tozaligi ustidan nazoratni o‘z ichiga oladi. Turizmda bu ikki tushuncha xizmat ko‘rsatish sifati bilan chambarchas bog‘liq bo‘lib, ayniqsa, ovqatlanish, yashash va transport xizmatlarida o‘z aksini topadi. Gigiyenaga amal qilinmasligi infeksiyon kasalliklarning tarqalishiga, sayyohlar salomatligining buzilishiga, mamlakat turistik imidjining pasayishiga olib keladi. Ayniqsa, pandemiya tajribasi shuni ko‘rsatdiki, turizmda sanitariya madaniyati — raqobatbardoshlikning asosiy omiliga aylangan.

Xalqaro gigiyena va sanitariya standartlari: ISO va HACCP tizimlari

Bugungi kunda turizmda gigiyena va sanitariya xavfsizligini ta‘minlashda xalqaro standartlar muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ularning eng muhimlari quyidagilardir: ISO 22000 — oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi menejmenti tizimi bo‘lib, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarining iste‘molchiga yetkazilguncha har bir bosqichda xavfsizligini ta‘minlashni ko‘zda tutadi. HACCP (Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points) — xavf tahlili va muhim nazorat nuqtalari tizimi. Bu tizim har qanday sanitariya tahdidini oldindan aniqlab, ularni bartaraf etishga yordam beradi.

Xalqaro miqyosda faoliyat yuritayotgan mehmonxona va restoran tarmoqlari aynan shu tizimlar asosida ishlaydi. Bu tizimlarning joriy qilinishi xodimlar malakasini oshirish, ichki nazorat tizimini kuchaytirish, mijoz ishonchini ta‘minlash imkonini beradi.

O‘zbekistonda mavjud holat: qonunchilik va amaliy tajriba.

O‘zbekiston gigiyena va sanitariya talablari bo‘yicha bir nechta me‘yoriy hujjatlariga ega: O‘zbekiston Respublikasining “Sanitariya-epidemiologik osoyishtalik to‘g‘risida”gi Qonuni Davlat sanitariya normalari va qoidalari; Turizm va madaniy meros vazirligining xizmat sifati bo‘yicha reglamentlari. Amalda esa yirik shaharlar (Toshkent, Samarqand, Buxoro)dagi turistik obyektlarda gigiyena madaniyati nisbatan yuqori darajada, zamonaviy talablarga javob beradi. Biroq, ayrim viloyatlar (jumladan, Jizzax, Sirdaryo, Qashqadaryo)da kichik mehmonxonalar va oilaviy restoranlar zamonaviy gigiyenik standartlarga to‘liq javob bermaydi. Muammo, asosan, xodimlarning malakasi pastligi, sanitariya vositalari va bilim yetishmasligida namoyon bo‘ladi.

Xalqaro standartlarga mos sertifikatlash tizimini joriy etish – Mehmonxonalar va restoranlarga ISO yoki HACCP bo‘yicha baho berilishi ularning raqobatbardoshligini oshiradi.

Talim va malaka oshirish dasturlarini yo‘lga qo‘yish – Xodimlar uchun gigiyena madaniyati bo‘yicha majburiy treninglar tashkil qilish.

Hududiy monitoring tizimini kuchaytirish – Har bir viloyatda gigiyena nazoratini mustahkamlash, ayniqsa turizm zonalarida.

Raqamli yechimlardan foydalanish – Dezinfeksiya va tozalikni nazorat qilishda sun‘iy intellekt, monitoring ilovalari va texnologiyalarni joriy etish.

Ommaviy axborot vositalari orqali targ‘ibot – Gigiyena madaniyati ommaviy ong darajasida yuksalishi lozim.

Xulosa

Xizmat ko‘rsatish sifati turizmning asosiy poydevoridir. Bu sohada gigiyena va sanitariya madaniyatini rivojlantirish orqali turistlarning ishonchi va mamnunligini ta‘minlash mumkin. O‘zbekiston bu borada muhim qadamlar tashlamoqda, ammo xalqaro tajribalar asosida tizimli yondashuv talab etiladi. Xalqaro standartlar asosida sertifikatlash, malaka oshirish va zamonaviy texnologiyalarni qo‘llash orqali O‘zbekiston turizmini yanada jahon darajasiga olib chiqish mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

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